

ENCOURAGING STUDENTS TO CREATIVE THINKING THROUGH ADAPTATION TO THE LEARNING PROCESS

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ANNOTATION

This article presents information about how students' adaptation to the educational process can be influenced by their personal characteristics and mental activity, i.e. ways of forming a way of thinking that characterizes its focus on professional activity.

Keywords: professional, adaptation, professional competencies, heredity, social development, student adaptation period, biological, psychological, social development.

ПООЩЕНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ К ТВОРЧЕСКОМУ МЫШЛЕНИЮ ЧЕРЕЗ АДАПТАЦИЮ К ПРОЦЕССУ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены сведения о том, каким образом на адаптацию студентов к образовательному процессу могут влиять их личностные особенности и мыслительная деятельность, т. е. способы формирования образа мышления, характеризующего его направленность на профессиональную деятельность.

Ключевые слова: профессионал, адаптация, профессиональные компетенции, наследственность, социальное развитие, период адаптации студента, биологическое, психологическое, социальное развитие.

TALABALARNI O‘QUV JARAYONIGA MOSLASHISHI ORQALI IJODIY FIKRLASHGA UNDASH.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada talabalarning ta’lim jarayoniga moslashishi ularning shaxsiy xususiyatlari va aqliy faoliyati, ya’ni uning kasbiy faoliyatga yo’naltirilganligini tavsiflovchi fikrlash tarzini shakllantirish usullari qanday ta’sir qilishi mumkinligi haqida ma’lumot beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *kasbiy, moslashuv, kasbiy kompetensiyalar, irsiyat, ijtimoiy rivojlanish, o‘quvchilarning moslashuv davri, biologik, psixologik, ijtimoiy rivojlanish.*

Setting the problem: It is known that an educational institution, where a person spends one of the most important periods of his life, is formed as a professional and a person, is considered an important component of this environment. During the educational and professional activity, the student acquires the most important professional competencies in order to achieve the necessary professional level, in which professional qualities are formed, the professional goals of the person and the requirements of the profession are coordinated, that is, adaptation to professional activity takes place will give.

The formation of students’ adaptation to the educational process can be characterized by the following concepts as their personal characteristics:

firstly, from the psychological side - the unity of psychological processes, states and properties of a person. From the psychological point of view, the main ones are mental properties (direction, temperament, character, abilities), the course of mental processes, the occurrence of mental states, and the manifestation of mental structures depend on them. However, while studying a specific student, along with the above, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of each individual, his mental processes and conditions;

secondly, from the social side, the levels of social relations, communication and influence arising from the student’s belonging to a certain social group, nation, etc.;

thirdly, from the biological side, the type of higher nervous activity, the function of the analyzers, unconditioned reflexes, instincts, physical strength, body structure,

facial features, skin, eye color, wealth and other characteristics are mainly related to heredity and those who are born, and are influenced by living conditions may vary by a certain amount.

Research method: The organization of these aspects reveals the student's personal qualities and capabilities, his age-related and personal characteristics. Compared to other age periods, the highest speed of quick memory and attention shifting, verbal-logical tasks are mentioned in adolescence. Thus, the adaptation period of the student is characterized by reaching the highest peaks based on all previous stages of biological, psychological and social development. [1]

According to B. G. Ananov, student age is a sensitive period for the development of the main sociogenic potentials of a person. The educational process in higher education and the social environment in it have a great impact on the student's psyche and the development of his personal qualities. In the educational process of vocational training, the ability to focus the student's mental activity, that is, forms a way of thinking that describes the person's focus on professional activity. To successfully flow in higher education requires a much higher level of general intellectual development, including perception, imagination, memory, thinking, attention, erudition, breadth of knowledge interests, mastery of logical operations, and so on. When the level of knowledge decreases a little, it can be replenished for a certain period of time due to such qualities as motivation or work ability, conscientiousness, thoroughness and neatness in educational activities. But there are limits to the decline of such activity, beyond which the subsequent replenishment mechanisms do not help, and the student can be excluded from the flow. These levels vary slightly in different HEIs, but in general, they are almost the same, even when comparing HEIs in the capital and provinces, which are considered prestigious and not so prestigious.

Results of the research: the necessary condition for success in the student's work is to reduce the characteristics of flow in the higher education institution, which is new for him. So, it shows as little influence as possible to eliminate the feeling of internal discomfort (discomfort) and prevent conflicts with the environment. In the initial courses, a team of students is formed, the knowledge and skills of correct mental activity are developed, the chosen profession is understood, the optimal work and rest schedule is organized, and a work system for education and upbringing is established. [3]

A psychophysiological condition discovered by I.P. Pavlov, which forms a dynamic stereotype, can lead to nervous tension and stress reactions at the base of a sharp collapse of the working stereotype. Therefore, the adjustment period associated with the use of previous stereotypes is likely to cause both low attrition and communication difficulties at first. In some students, the formation of a new stereotype

is observed in leaps and bounds, while in others, it occurs at a steady pace. Undoubtedly, the peculiarities of such sudden changes are related to the characteristics of the type of higher nervous activity, but social factors play a decisive role in this. Knowing the individual characteristics of the student, building the introduction to new types of activities and a new circle of communication as its basis helps to prevent the disadaptation syndrome and make the adaptation process uniform and psychologically comfortable.

In order to look at the process of adaptation of students in the conditions of lower vocational education courses, it is necessary to reveal the peculiarities of some of its constituent elements.

Adaptation of students in the social environment is characterized by the structural and functional components of the higher education system. In the process of adaptation, the student must understand the purpose of the educational system, get into it, and master the unique methods of education.

A student, or a group of students, or a small group of students can appear as an element of adaptation to the educational process of higher education, in which case they are not necessarily related to the educational framework.

It is possible to distinguish the following conditions in the adaptation activities of the students of the first stage of the educational process of higher educational institutions:

- novelty of the student's goals;
- the novelty of the activities that take place within the educational process of higher educational institutions;
- new relationships in his social environment;
- the novelty of the social environment that requires adaptation to urban conditions for students from rural areas. [2]

The need for accommodation may or may not be perceived by the student. When the need for adaptation is not understood, the student, seeing that the previous methods of activity and behavior are impossible, spontaneously looks for other methods by trial and error, as a result, adaptation is slow and with great difficulties.

The need for adaptation can be met by a student at two levels:

- OTM level, in which the necessary external conditions are created for the implementation (realization) of the need for adaptation;
- personal level, in which the need to adapt becomes the driving force of the individual's self-education and self-discipline.

In the process of developing the need for adaptation, the following main problems can be distinguished

- the occurrence of inconsistency between the person and the social environment. It can occur in different sub-structures of a person (motives, enthusiasm, knowledge, skills, qualifications) as a result of objective activity or personal environment;
- the student's experience of this inconsistency in the form of mental tension, anxiety, change in cognitive adaptation (dissonance);
- the understanding of this inconsistency by the student, the establishment of motives and the realization of adaptation;
- design of adaptation goal, plan, individual strategy and tactics by the student.

In order to overcome various conflicts faced by the teacher during his daily activities with the students, high level communication experience and skills are required. The basis of such skills is the use of humane technologies, avoidance of blindness, and close communication with students. If the educator does not look for a way to eliminate the differences between the parties, does not bring the relations between the students closer to each other, does not direct the arising problems to a cooperative solution, does not seek commonality of opinion, then the interpersonal conflict will remain. Despite the difference in tasks and social roles of educators and students, they are united by the form of cooperative activity. [4]

The interpretation of the social approach to the concept of adaptation, the professional adaptation of students to the process of higher education and preparation for the profession, the issues of adaptation to professional activity were discussed by scientists of our republic A.Davletshin, E.G'oziev, Y.Akhmadaliev, N.Ismatova, G'.Shaumarov, Sh.Khalilova, N.A.Muslimov, U.N. Nishonaliev, M.B. Bekmurodov, I.A. Gazizova, B.H. Rakhimovlar, scientists from CIS countries E.M. Avramova, E.A. Aleksandrova, T.Ashchepkov, O.A.Abdulina, S.A.Dmitrienko, A.P.Kormilitsyn, E.N.Ryabinova, G.F.Tokareva, T.V.Christidis, etc. who have studied the issues related to their adaptation to the social environment and having their own place and status.

In the process of social adaptation, a student of the first stage is considered not only an object, but also a subject, an element of complex, even conflicting relations that arise in the interaction (cooperation) of "teacher - student", "student - student", "student - group", "administration - student". "Teacher-student" interaction is more and more indicative, especially at the first stage, it determines the content of life activities of students in the educational environment of HEIs. The role of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions in the adaptation of first-level students is leading and extremely important, teachers are involved in this process both in the study of academic subjects and in extracurricular activities with students. In this direction, the role of academic group coaches is very important. The analysis of studies on the adaptation of students to higher education allows us to come to the following conclusions:

- both the object and subjects of the educational process are considered in the adaptation of teachers and upper level students to the educational process of the first level students;

- the typology of the interaction (cooperation) of the social and cultural environment of the higher education institution with the student should form the basis of the planning of work directions for the adaptation of the first-level students;

- it is necessary to carry out targeted work on identifying the symptoms of students' disadaptation (difficulty to adapt), and organize special work with them in the future;

- it is necessary to study the first levels of adaptation of each student's personality to external influences, to develop a phased adaptation process based on the classification (separation) of students of the first stage, and to organize relevant activities;

- changing the valuable directions of students should be one of the directions of adaptation monitoring; - it is required to carry out activities aimed at mastering as many social roles as possible by students of the first stage, to ensure the activity of student self-management bodies in the process of mastering.

Based on the social, psychological and pedagogical foundations of the effective adaptation of students to the educational process of the higher educational institution, as well as the innovative systematic approach, the possibilities of developing the conceptual foundations of their adaptation to the educational process were established.

It is called "Pedagogical and methodical possibilities of students' adaptation to the educational process", in which the essence of students' adaptation to the educational process, the model of improving the organizational pedagogical conditions of students' adaptation to the educational process, professional self-awareness, professional competence, professional reflexivity, professional behavior qualities, methods of organizing the process of professional adaptation based on the technology of pedagogical conflict management, technology of improving the activity of the teacher-coach were discussed.

On the basis of the technology of mutual conflict management, an improved methodology was developed for the topic "Pedagogical conflicts arising in pedagogical activity between the teacher and the student in the student's self-awareness, their causes and elimination measures". In the lesson, a technological model and map of the lesson was developed based on the application of conflict management technology to the process of professional adaptation based on the formation of self-awareness of professional qualities, competence, level of reflexivity and professional behavior skills.

Based on the structure of the model, firstly, the goal, theoretical foundations (approaches, principles), the content of working with students to improve the content

of adaptation to the educational process of the higher education institution based on the organizational and pedagogical conditions; innovative educational forms and methods, organizational pedagogical conditions for adaptation to the educational process, adaptation indicators, criteria for increasing adaptation levels and organizational aspects of implementation of adaptation level indicators (high, medium, low) are also covered.

It is called "Effectiveness of the oriented pedagogical system of adaptation of students of higher education institutions to the educational process" and it contains the research results of didactic, psychological, social adaptation of students through research, as well as understanding of national identity, values as a priority problem, and professional flexibility. At the same time, indicators of factors of national identity awareness in the social adaptation of students to the educational process, pedagogical conditions for successful adaptation of students to the educational process, and experimental work on effective didactic adaptation of students to the educational process are highlighted.

The research work was carried out on the basis of questionnaire survey, experimental work with 232 first-level students of Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, "Vocational Education" direction of Karshi State Universities and other directions from September 2016 to May 2018. received.

As a result of conducting psychological-pedagogical work with the students of the first stage, that is, in the process of conducting it based on the program of the special course developed by us and giving the necessary recommendations, it was found that most students understand the difficulties of adaptation and each student can take an individual approach to solving their problems.

Pedagogical conditions for student adaptation in control and experimental test groups with students of the first stage of experimental work: organization of psychological-pedagogical support that shapes students' adaptation to the educational process (implementation of a special course program), organization of cooperation between students and management, with the help of coaches in the group creating an educational environment, respecting the personality of the student, eliminating conflict situations in the group in a timely manner, organizing a moral environment in student residences.

Comparing the control group to each of the experimental groups based on the Pearson χ^2 (chi-square) test, we obtained the following results:

Tk.(1-TG, NG) = 2.12; Tkuzat.(2-TG, NG) = 0.39; Tkuzat.(3-TG, NG) = 3.06; Tkuzat.(4-TG, NG) = 7.08; Ttanq.=6.64. Based on the results obtained in this way, we observe a difference in the 4th experiment (4-TG) group compared to the control (NG)

group Tkuzat.> Ttanq.. No significant difference was observed in the 2nd experiment group (2-TG) (Tkuzat. <<Ttanq.). 1-TG and 3-TG groups were also significantly less different from the control group (NG) (Tkuzat.< Ttanq.).

The result of the observation during the experimental stage showed that the students of the experimental group positively and highly evaluated the influence of the group leaders' support on adaptation to the educational process. A questionnaire aimed at assessing the adaptation of the requirements of the first stage to the educational process was conducted among students at the end of the academic year (Table 2).

Table 2

Indicators of students' assessment of the levels of adaptation to the educational process

Evaluation indicators	Ratings in percent (%)					
	Control group			Experimental group		
	high	medium	low	high	medium	low
The process of interaction (worldview) in OTM	-	32,5%	67,5%	70,0%	30,0%	-
Level of social activity	-	65,0%	35,0%	15,0%	70,0%	15,0%
Level of satisfaction with the educational process	10,0%	90,0%	-	33,5%	62,5%	-
Total score obtained from all academic subjects taught in the first stage	3,0 ball			3,7 ball		

Analyzing the results of the questionnaire obtained between the requirements of the control body and the experimental group, we found out that among the students, 10.0% of the requirements of the control group - high level, 90.0% of students - medium level; 100% in the requirements of the experience group - average level (high, medium). Students of the communication drug control organization have a high level of broad and social activity, acceptance of control group requirements. As a result - average score, the experimental group during the first semester - 3.7 points, and the requirements of the control group - 3.0 points (on a 5-point system).

Figure 2. Obtained among students of the control group experimental results

Figure 3. It was obtained among the students of the experimental group experimental results

Table 3 shows the positive and negative effects of first-year students’ adaptation to the educational process.

3 – table

Factors influencing the adaptation of the first stage students to the educational processes of the educational institution.

Evaluation parameters	In the beginning grade point averages, in points (M)		In the end grade point averages, in points (M)		Reliability Mn/ Mt
	Mn	Mt	Mn	Mt	
Талабалар мослашишига ижобий таъсир этувчи омиллар:					
Parental support	2,6	2,7	2,9	3,2	
Educator support	2,9	2,8	3,1	3,2	
Support of group leaders	2,3	2,3	2,1	4,0	*
Support from teammates	3,3	3,6	2,9	3,9	*
Spiritual-educational department and work with students, support of the trade union	1,4	1,5	1,8	1,9	
Active participation in collective work of higher education institutions	3,3	3,5	2,8	3,8	*
Adapting students - problematic factors					
With his bandmates	1,7	1,5	1,5	1,1	
With educators	2,1	2,5	2,2	2,0	
With health	2,5	1,9	2,1	1,5	
With the inability to learn special subjects	2,6	2,8	2,5	2,0	*
With mistakes made in occupation	1,9	1,7	1,7	1,5	

At this stage of our research, a questionnaire on "Assessment of national identity awareness of students in adaptation to the educational process" was developed and put into practice. At this stage, the overall average indicators of factors affecting students' socio-political adjustment were higher than the average at the beginning of the experiment and at the end of the experiment (2.51 ± 0.19 and 2.63 ± 0.28). This shows that, although their results are at the same level, statistically, the rate of completion of the experiment is partially higher (the difference has a reliability ratio of $t=3.66$, $p \leq 0.001$).

It can be seen that the necessity of following the rule of taking into account the psychological, age and specific characteristics of students in the implementation of the problem of facilitating the adaptation of higher education students to the educational process has been proven in experience.

Conclusion

The results of theoretical research and experimental work on improving the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the adaptation of students of the first stage to the educational process allow making the following conclusions:

1. The concept of "adaptation" was studied in extended depth. It is determined by three types (psychological, social and pedagogical) of students' adaptation to the educational process in the context of the modernization of the higher education system, as well as a set of 3 components: formal, general and didactic. Concepts such as "adaptation", "flexibility", "pedagogical conditions" were explained. The concept of "adaptation" is a concept in a broad sense, which means the creation of conditions for students' active actions and their effective results, as well as the integration of a person into a new environment without conflicts.

2. For the students of the "Professional Education" baccalaureate courses, "Educational Work Methodology" in the field of "Educational Work Methodology", the nature of pedagogical disagreements and the nature of pedagogical disagreements about the pedagogical conflicts that arise between the teacher and the student and the measures to eliminate them, in order to develop the skills of adapting to the learning process knowing the content and types, the causes and prevention measures, from the field of "Educational Work Methodology" "The subject of the topic of mutual conflict management technology based on the technology developed a takomiliziye methodology.

3. In the context of the modernization of higher education institutions, a model of didactic and professional training was developed for the educational process of the first stage students in the field of irrigation and improvement, the social demand (order), purpose, pedagogical conditions, training stages, activity types and forms, application of advanced technologies, training results and he took others into himself. Diagnostic materials have been developed and benchmarks have been identified to facilitate the learning process of OTM students.

Different forms of adaptation: pedagogical (interactions in the group, sharing knowledge, skills and abilities), social (socialization, self-awareness based on values), psychological (personal excitement, psycho-emotional mental experiences, mental stress), and an indicator of adaptation of the first stage students to the educational process (indicator) were scientifically based.

4. Specific characteristics and nature of adaptation of students of higher education institutions to the educational process, as well as organizational and pedagogical conditions for adaptation of students were determined. In the process of modernization of education, the pedagogical conditions for optimizing the effective

adaptation of students of the first stage to the educational process were scientifically based: the content, form, methods, technologies of activity.

5. The special course (18 hours) entitled "Adaptation of students of the first stage of higher education institutions to the educational process" was proved to lead to the optimization of students' adaptation to the educational process.

6. Factors that facilitate adaptation to the educational process of the higher education system are implemented through the implementation of uniformity of complex standards and requirements in all systems. For formation of adaptation of higher education students to the educational process, students should organize a socio-political complex with the condition of increasing their activity.

7. The adaptation process of students is based on the technology of mutual pedagogical conflicts in three stages: pedagogical experiment-test works based on the Pearson χ^2 (chi-square) criterion, the result of the experimental group was higher than the control group, and the effectiveness of the chosen methodology was justified.

Research conducted within the scope of this scientific article is not possible to cover all aspects of the problems of effective adaptation of first-level students to higher education institutions. Therefore, in order to further improve the theoretical-methodological, methodical and practical directions of effective adaptation of students to the educational process, the following recommendations were presented:

- taking the adaptation of first-level students to the educational process as a pedagogical problem, and solving this problem, we developed a special course program called "Effective adaptation of first-level students of higher education institutions to the educational process", a model for improving the pedagogical conditions of students' adaptation to the educational process, to ensure the direct participation of the leadership of higher education institutions, youth union, faculties and group leaders in the implementation of indicators of adaptation to the conditions and educational process;

- To substantiate the provision of effective adaptation of students to the educational process through social and psychological adaptation based on the principle of "teacher-student" and through the necessary pedagogical methods and tools;

- psychologists of higher educational institutions should help students to overcome pedagogical stress, strong fear, and mental stress under the influence of pedagogical conditions of the new educational system during education and training.

The conducted researches led to facilitating the effective adaptation of students to the educational process of higher education institutions. The research work conducted in this direction will help to facilitate the process of adaptation in higher education institutions of various directions and to improve the professional characteristics of future specialists.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Mirziyoev SH.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 488 p.
2. Golubeva N. M. Diagnostic level adaptation of students to professional detailing. Methodological recommendations. - Chelyabinsk: CHGAKI, 2002. - 60 p.
3. Jilina L.A. Adaptation of students to the educational environment of the university: teaching method/L.A. Zhilina. - Omsk: Izd-vo "Poligrafichesky center KAN", 2008. - 60 p.
4. Inoyatov U.I. Theoretical and organizational-methodical basic management control of quality education and professional college. Diss. ... Dr. ped. science - Tashkent, 2003. - 327 p.
5. Mukumova D.I. Temirova Z.I. Creation of pedagogical conditions of modern pedagogic technologies in the training process of professional education specialists. JOURNAL OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION AND RESEARCH. SEPTEMBER-2022/<https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/issue/view/9/> VOLUME 2022_1_4
6. D.I. Muqumova. Pedagogical conflicts in the pedagogical activities of water management, their causes and measures to eliminate them. No. 2(28). 2022 Journal of "Irrigation and melioration", p. 90.
7. Mukumova D.I. Osobennosti adaptatsii studentov v uchebnyy protsess // Metodicheskoe posobie. - TIMI, 2016. - 61 p.
8. Mukumova D.I. Adaptation of students to uchebnoy deyatelnosti v vysshey shkole // Eastern European Scientific Journal, Germany, 2018. #3. -P. 305-307. (13.00.00, No. 1.
9. Mukumova D.I. Pedagogicheskie usloviya povyshenia adaptatsii studentov pervogo kursa k uchebnomu protsessu // Public education. - Tashkent, 2018. - No. 4. - B. 138-142. (13.00.00, #17)
10. Zukhra Karabaevna Ismailova, Pulat Maxsudovich Maxsudov, Rustam Hamraevich Fayzullaev, Alisher Asatillaevich Zhumanov and Khayrulla Ergashovich Tuychiev Designing the Process of Education and Training of Future Teachers on the Basis of Individual Principles *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, Vol. 24, Issue 04, 2020 DOI: 10.37200/IJPR/V24I4/PR2020477 Pages: 6653-6659 <https://www.psychosocial.com/article/PR2020477/26967/>
11. Alisher Asatillaevich Jumanov Communication As A Process Of Interaction And Relationship Between People *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations* Published: January 25, 2021 | Pages: 164-169 <https://usajournalshub.com/index.php/tajssei/article/view/1895/1801>

12. Jumanov Alisher Asatullayevich, Ibragimova Gulzoda Nabievna, Abduraxmonova Shohi daxon Abduqodirovna Model Of Diagnostics And Improvement Of Quality Of Preparation For Professional Activity Based On Integration Of Pedagogical And Technical Knowledge *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations* Published: December 18, 2020 | Pages: 107-114 <https://usajournalshub.com/index.php/tajssei/article/view/1644/1562>

13. Z.K. Ismailova, M.X. Baybaeva, D. Mustafayeva, A. Jumanov Development of entrepreneurial skills among students of technical institutions through innovative technologies *Economics and Innovative Technologies* Volume 2020 Number 1 Issue1 Article 4 Pages: 1-8 <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1318&context=iqtisodiyot>

14. Jumanov Alisher Asatillaevich, Ibragimova Gulzoda Nabievna THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENT OF THE HEAD *SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF MODERN SOCIETY* Abstracts of VII International Scientific and Practical Conference Liverpool, United Kingdom 4-6 March 2020 101-107 <https://sci-conf.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/SCIENTIFIC-ACHIEVEMENTS-OF-MODERN-SOCIETY-4-6.03.2020.pdf>

15. Jumanov A.A. Development of technological competence in students based on an integrative approach. // ISSN 2749-0866 *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. Vol.2 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences* Pages: 727-731 b. <https://berlinstudies.de/index.php/berlinstudies/article/view/496/455>

16. Jumanov A.A. Communication As A Process Of Interaction And Relationship Between People. // ISSN – 2689-100x *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations* January 25, 2021 Volume03 Issue01-31 Pages: 164-169 b. <https://theamericanjournals.com/index.php/tajssei/article/view/1212/1134>

17. Jumanov A.A. Appropriate application of pedagogical communication methods in the educational process. // *Monografia pokonferencyjna Science, research, development #34 Paris 30.10.2020-31.10.2020 – P: 131-133.* http://xn--e1aajfpcds8ay4h.com.ua/files/106_01_xi_2020_s.pdf

18. Mukumova D.I. Soderjaniya pedagogicheskogo komponenta professionalnogo obrazovaniya kak faktor formirovaniya kompetentnosti studentov VUZA // *Pedagogical skill. -Bukhara, 2017. - No. 3, -B. 6-7. (13.00.00, No. 23)*